

Development and Validation of a Python-Based Probabilistic Tool for Simulating Pebble Motion in Pebble Bed Reactors

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ABSTRACT

Pebble Bed Reactors (PBRs) represent a promising class of advanced nuclear systems, thanks to their inherent safety features, continuous refueling capability, and flexible design. Nevertheless, their simulation remains challenging due to the dynamic behavior of the core, where thousands of fuel pebbles continuously move and experience varying neutron fluxes. The hyper-fidelity depletion tool (HxF), developed at UC Berkeley, has been proposed to address this issue by tracking individual pebble histories, coupling transport, depletion, and pebble motion. However, the current methods implemented within HxF for modeling pebble motion either lack geometric flexibility or are computationally intensive. In this work, a novel probabilistic approach to pebble motion is proposed. The method relies on stochastic sampling based on predefined velocity fields to approximate the physical trajectories of individual pebbles without explicitly resolving their mechanical interactions. By doing so, it achieves a balance between accuracy and computational efficiency. The algorithm is validated within a Python–Serpent coupled environment by simulating a quasi-realistic PBR system. The results demonstrate that the tool successfully reproduces the overall core behavior and the occurrence of outlier pebbles, in agreement with the reference study.

Keywords: Hyper-Fidelity Depletion, Monte Carlo Simulations, Pebble Bed Reactors, Pebble Motion Modeling

1. INTRODUCTION

The core of a PBR contains hundreds of thousands of graphite fuel pebbles, arranged in a densely packed bed. These pebbles are introduced from one end of the core and migrate slowly through it over time, undergoing progressive fuel depletion. The motion can be gravity-driven in case of a gas-cooled PBR or buoyancy-driven for the salt-cooled concept. Upon reaching the discharge outlet, pebbles that exceed a given burnup threshold are permanently discarded. Each pebble undergoes multiple full passes through the core before being discarded, thereby allowing it to reach higher burnup levels and reduce fuel costs. Because fresh fuel is continuously inserted and spent fuel is removed, PBRs can maintain criticality with minimal excess reactivity, thereby simplifying reactivity control and enhancing overall safety. Moreover, the absence of periodic shutdowns for refueling significantly increases reactor availability compared to traditional reactors operating under a batch refueling scheme. As the reactor operates, the core reaches a quasi-equilibrium state in which key parameters remain stable over time, despite the ongoing motion and replacement of individual fuel elements.

Due to their individual trajectories within the core, pebbles are exposed to different neutron spectra over time, resulting in a wide diversity of isotopic compositions. As such, precise motion modeling is crucial to supply the neutronics code with spatially accurate input data regarding the pebbles' position and trajectories. Properly simulating the insertion of fresh pebbles, the removal of spent fuel and the reinsertion of partially burned elements is critical for modeling reactor operation. Tracking

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the unique histories of hundreds of thousands of pebbles requires multiphysics simulations that couple pebble motion, fuel depletion, and thermal-hydraulics, necessitating complex computational frameworks and significant resources. Within this context, a high-resolution modeling approach, known as hyper-fidelity depletion (HxF) [1], has been introduced. HxF explicitly tracks each pebble within a full-scale 3D geometry. Each element is modeled with its own spatial position, evolving fuel composition, and temperature profile. To achieve this, a Python-based tool has been created, integrating Serpent 2 [2] for Monte Carlo neutron transport simulations, pebble motion routines, and the GeN-Foam [3] porous media solver for thermal-hydraulics.

HxF currently offers two pebble motion methods: Discrete Motion (DM) and Discrete Element Method (DEM). The DM method models pebble circulation by shuffling fuel compositions within a static lattice, rather than physically moving individual pebbles. It enables modeling of pebble movement with reduced computational complexity, avoiding the overhead associated with physical motion tracking. However, it has limitations in handling complex geometries and cannot model radial motion or varying pebble speeds. On the other hand, the DEM treats each pebble in the reactor as a distinct element, accurately capturing the mechanical interactions between the fuel elements and between pebbles and reactor walls or other structural elements. The DEM provides a realistic representation of pebble trajectories and offers greater flexibility in handling geometries with fueling chutes. However, it requires significant computational resources and tuning parameters.

The proposed motion method aims to reduce the simulation time by eliminating any physical modeling of pebble dynamics. It relies on probabilistic selection mechanisms to reproduce the key features of pebble motion within the core, including wall-induced friction effects, radial drift and spatially varying velocity profiles. At the same time, this approach remains applicable to more realistic core layouts, including those featuring refueling and defueling chutes.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1. 2D Model

To develop this method, firstly a 2D model is built based on the axial section of the generic Fluoride-Salt-Cooled High-Temperature Reactor (gFHR) [4]. This reactor design features a cylindrical core in which the pebbles are driven upward by buoyancy, then discharged at the top and reintroduced at the bottom. For this computational model, the pebbles are schematized as being arranged in a Face-Centered Cubic (FCC) lattice. The underlying algorithm randomly selects pebbles from each lattice layer and moves them upward. Because of the interactions with the walls, pebbles near the reflector travel more slowly than those moving through the core center, resulting in an approximately parabolic velocity profile, as described in [5]. To generate the Probability Density Function (PDF) required for random pebble selection, each pebble is assigned to a radial bin; the velocity profile is then discretized by computing the average velocity in each bin and normalized to obtain probability-like values.

Section 2.1 is a simplified representation of a motion step. Random pebbles, highlighted here in red, green and blue, respectively for the first, second and third layer, are selected to be moved upward (a). Next, the pebbles that will shift laterally, as they adjust to fill the void created by the upward movement, are identified and here highlighted in yellow (b). Finally, the bed is rearranged accordingly, completing the motion step (c). The pebble extracted from the top layer, i.e. the red one, is reinserted at the bottom of the bed, mimicking the circulation outside the core. For each simulated day, the bed rearrangement caused by the recirculation of a single pebble is repeated for a number of times equal to the circulation rate, which is the quantity defining the average pass residence time of the pebbles. Results from the 2D simulation are shown in Section 2.1. The pass residence time increases linearly with the elevation, meaning that as the pebbles migrate upward, they tend to accumulate residence time at a constant rate. It can be observed that the values near the wall are slightly higher than those at the center of the core, indicating that the tool is able to reproduce the wall effects. The ratio decreases sharply from the bottom

Figure 1. Schematic representation of a motion step (left) and pass residence time along the core (right)

of the core, stabilizing at approximately 1.057, with a standard deviation of 0.051. The initial behavior is due to the fact that the residence time is close to zero at the bottom, causing the ratio to assume relatively high values in this region.

At this stage, in anticipation of extending the model to more complex geometries that include refueling and defueling chutes, the impact of a 2-variables velocity field is explored. Since the 2D model runs in just a few seconds, a sensitivity analysis on the velocity field can be readily performed to better reproduce the DEM results reported in [1] for the same core model. The effect of introducing a logarithmic axial increase of the speed ratio, the latter being defined for each layer as the ratio between the maximum and the minimum speed, is shown in Figure 2. The ratio between the pass residence time near the walls and that at the center is used as a metric, dividing the core into axial slices and computing this quantity for each of them. The values from both the 2D simulations are compared with those coming from the DEM: at the core outlet, the simulation with a 1-variable field exhibits a cumulative deviation of 31% from the DEM, whereas the 2-variables field reduces it to 19.35%. It is evident that the velocity field affects the results. Although the presence of extraction chutes is the primary factor inducing an axial dependence of the velocity field within the core, as discussed in [5], the DEM model reveals a mild axial effect even in a simple cylindrical configuration. Therefore, feeding the algorithm a more complex velocity field improves the prediction of the pass residence time.

Figure 2. Axial cumulative difference with respect to the DEM

2.2. 3D Model

Since the 2D model proves that it is possible to reproduce the wall effects with a probabilistic motion method, it can be generalized to a 3D system using the same approach. Again, a PDF for random peb-

bles extraction is required, but in this case the three dimensional geometry comes with an additional challenge and a numerical procedure is needed in order to obtain the correct pebble sampling probability [6]. Since the simulation time is expected to grow significantly, a reduced version of the gFHR is used to test the 3D model. Two different motion algorithms have been developed: the Random Path Generation Algorithm (RPGA) and the Axial Channels Algorithm (ACA) [6]. The first one simulates a rearrangement of each lattice layer for every circulating pebble and, despite being more realistic, the number of operations performed per inner cycle is quite high. Since the computational cost of this algorithm is significant, a tool entirely based on it would not fulfill the primary objective of this work. The pebble motion simulation within the reduced gFHR took 1 hour and 45 minutes to be completed, with an expected time required for the actual gFHR simulation of 50 hours. The second algorithm working principle is much easier, thus it is also much faster: a pebble is selected randomly in the top layer, and the one in the layer below is chosen from one of the available positions immediately around the first pebble. By repeating this operation along the entire core height, an axial channel of upward-moving pebbles is generated. Although this method partially limits the radial motion, the same simulation runs in just 11 minutes.

Both the 1-variable and the 2-variables velocity fields have been tested, and the pebble sorting probability correction procedure has been applied in order to obtain physically meaningful pass residence time distributions. Figure 3 shows the results obtained with the ACA; for the reported global parameters there is not significant difference between the two cases, hence only the results from the 1-variable field simulation are shown. Also in a 3D configuration, the wall effects are clearly reproduced, as there are outlier pebbles either moving faster or slower than the average.

Figure 3. Average pass residence time over multiple passes (left) and pass residence time distribution (right).

Although the RPGA is computationally intensive, it is required to handle specific layers in conical reactor configurations. In these regions, with the pebbles embedded in a FCC lattice, some of them do not have neighboring fuel elements in the layer below, which would cause the ACA to fail during the pebble selection phase. Thus, in order to simulate pebble motion within the more realistic reactor geometry including fueling and defueling chutes, both the algorithms have been applied.

3. VALIDATION FRAMEWORK

To validate the pebble motion algorithm, a simplified simulation environment was developed to reproduce the main functionalities of HxF. A Python script initializes the reactor geometry according to user-defined input parameters and, once the burnup step length in days is defined, a Bash script automatically handles the entire workflow by sequentially running Serpent 2 and executing Python scripts.

Upon completion of the transport and burnup calculations, the pebble motion is simulated with a Python script for a duration equal to the burnup step length. The average pass residence time, which is used to calculate the corresponding circulation rate, is the only input required at this stage. Finally, another Python script is executed to extract and save the relevant data in a pebble bed status file. In addition, discharged pebbles that meet the discard criteria are replaced with fresh ones. For every pebble, the status file reports several quantities of interest for post-processing, such as spatial coordinates, pass number, insertion step, power and accumulated burnup. It also includes boolean flags indicating whether each pebble has been discharged or discarded. Global reactor parameters, such as the multiplication factor and the conversion ratio, are stored in a separate file. The user may decide whether to save the detailed isotopic composition of all the pebbles, as well as the pebble-wise neutron flux data.

This environment was specifically designed to compare the results of the simulation based on the novel motion algorithm with those reported in [1]. Simulations were carried out on reduced versions of the gFHR. These configurations, containing slightly more than 6000 pebbles, represent the practical limit on a standard computer with 16 GB of RAM and 12 CPUs. Although different geometries are tested, the results should remain qualitatively consistent with those obtained with HxF, particularly in terms of outlier pebbles prediction and reactor dynamics representation.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results obtained from two different applications are presented and discussed. The set of scripts was initially tested on a simplified cylindrical geometry using the DM approach. The aim of this preliminary application is to ensure that the simulation environment works correctly in all its aspects; moreover, the results of this test case serve as a benchmark for the second application, which involves the implementation of the probabilistic motion algorithm in a more realistic configuration, featuring both refueling and defueling chutes.

Figure 4. Vertical cross-sections of the two Serpent 2 models: simplified cylindrical geometry (left) and conical geometry with refueling and defueling chutes (right).

Figure 4 shows the Serpent 2 models of the two geometries. Beside the geometric differences, the two simulations are basically equivalent. The core temperature is uniform and equal to 900 K, while the fuel temperature is 959 K. The pebble bed has a regular FCC structure, whereas the TRISO particles within the graphite matrix are arranged in a Simple Cubic (SC) lattice. The thickness of the reflector surrounding the active region is 30 cm. Since a core of this size could not reach criticality with the typical enrichment level of 19.9 wt-%, a 90 wt-% enrichment is used for these applications. This is clearly an unrealistic value, but the simulations are merely intended to test the tool.

The circulation rate is chosen in order to obtain the same average pass residence time, namely 30 days.

In the case of the conical geometry, Figure 5a shows how the presence of the defueling chute drastically increases the pass residence time of the pebbles moving close to the reactor walls. The discard threshold is based on the maximum number of passes through the core, in this case set to 5, and 20 full passes are simulated. On the neutronics side, transport and burnup calculations are based on the histories of 2×10^6 active neutrons and 4×10^5 inactive neutrons. Unfortunately, it was not possible to increase the number of histories, as it would have increased the computational time. It should therefore be noted that core-wise parameters convergence may not have been reached, and that increasing the number of active and inactive histories would likely lead to slightly different equilibrium values and lower uncertainties. However, this does not compromise the validity of the conclusions.

The most relevant core-wise parameters in the design of such systems are the multiplication factor, the conversion ratio and the power peaking factor. The time evolution of the first and the third is shown in Figure 5b for the conical geometry. Only the results for this configuration are presented, as no significant differences are observed in the behavior of these parameters, apart from their equilibrium values. In this case, the conversion ratio is not reported because, due to the very low initial concentration of ^{238}U , its equilibrium value is below 3% and thus negligible.

Figure 5

The behavior of these quantities is consistent with that reported in the reference study. The multiplication factor initially drops rapidly due to the accumulation of ^{135}Xe [1], then continues to decrease more gradually and stabilizes after 5 passes, i.e. 150 days, at an equilibrium value of 1.0242 ± 12 pcm, with a standard deviation of 98 pcm. The cyclic behavior of the multiplication factor is due to the gradual loss of fissile material and the accumulation of fission products in the pebbles, which are replaced by fresh ones once they reach the predefined discard threshold. The power peaking factor, on the other hand, remains stable throughout the simulation at a value of 1.777 ± 0.0098 , with a standard deviation of 0.043. The reason is that the peaking factor at each time step is determined by the neutron flux experienced by the pebbles and their fissile content, and both quantities oscillate in time around an average value.

Some interesting considerations can be drawn from Figure 6, which compares the current pass burnup spatial profiles. For the conical geometry, both profiles are limited to the active region, i.e. the cylindrical part of the core. The radial profile is nearly flat for the cylindrical core, with a slight increase at the periphery due to the higher thermal flux values close to the reflector. In the conical case, the walls have

a significant impact, leading to more pronounced differences between the central and outer regions. Both profiles show outlier pebbles accumulating far more burnup than the average.

Figure 6. Radial (left) and axial (right) current pass burnup profiles comparison between the two cases.

Additional insight comes from Figure 7 and Figure 8, showing the burnup distributions per pass of in-core, discharged and discarded pebbles. It can be seen that the distribution tends to assume a Gaussian shape as the pass number increases: the peaks observed in the distribution for the first pass, associated with the insertion of fresh pebbles, tend to smooth out. A progressive widening of the range of burnup values is also observed, due to the different paths pebbles can take inside the core. This causes overlap between the distributions as the pass number increases, such that, for example, pebbles with the same burnup level and three different pass numbers coexist in the core. Regarding the discharged pebbles, the distribution for pass number 5 coincides, due to the discard criterion based on the maximum number of passes, with that of the discarded pebbles.

Figure 7. Cylindrical geometry: in-core (left) and discharge (center) burnup distributions per pass, and discard burnup distribution (right).

The tails of the burnup distributions are much more pronounced for the conical geometry, causing increased overlap between the curves. While the average in-core burnup is comparable between the two cases, the presence of the defueling chute causes the discard burnup distribution to be more skewed toward higher values, reaching a maximum of 82.23 MWd/kg_U, against an end value of 51.25 MWd/kg_U for the cylindrical geometry.

Overall, the results indicate a larger spread between the maximum and minimum accumulated burnup compared with that observed in [1]. This behavior is likely driven by the small size of the core, which produces strong flux gradients between the central region and the reflector, leading to higher peaking factors and further amplifying the effect of the walls.

Figure 8. Conical geometry: in-core (left) and discharge (center) burnup distributions per pass, and discard burnup distribution (right).

5. CONCLUSIONS

This work presents the development and validation of a probabilistic algorithm for simulating pebble motion in PBRs. The proposed method is designed to overcome the limitations of traditional approaches, namely the inability to handle complex geometries of the DM method and the high computational cost of the DEM. The core idea of this novel approach is to replace explicit physical modeling of pebble trajectories with probabilistic selection schemes informed by predefined velocity fields. This allows the algorithm to simulate complex geometries and motion features, such as radial drift and wall effects, while drastically reducing the simulation time.

A custom simulation environment was built to test and validate the method under quasi-realistic conditions. Two test cases were simulated: a simplified cylindrical configuration and a more realistic core with refueling and defueling chutes. In both cases, the simulation converged to an equilibrium state. The results demonstrated that the new motion algorithm coherently reproduces global core behavior and the presence of outlier pebbles. Despite its strengths, the method depends on prior knowledge of the velocity field within the core. However, this limitation can be addressed by providing velocity data from DEM simulations or experimental campaigns, or by using the 2D model for preliminary sensitivity studies. Future work may focus on implementing the method in C++ to benefit from faster execution and native OpenMP parallelization, as well as integrating it within the HxF framework and testing it in the context of more realistic full-core simulations.

REFERENCES

- [1] Y. Robert. *Hyper-fidelity depletion in pebble bed reactors*. Ph.D. thesis, University of California, Berkeley (2023).
- [2] J. Leppänen, V. Valtavirta, A. Rintala, and R. Tuominen. "Status of Serpent Monte Carlo code in 2024." *EPJ Nuclear Sciences and Technologies* (2025).
- [3] C. Fiorina. "The GeN-Foam Multiphysics Solver: A Status Update." In *Proceedings of the PHYSOR 2022 Conference* (2022).
- [4] K. Power. URL <https://kairospower.com/>. Accessed: June 2025.
- [5] S. H. Kim, H. C. Kim, J. K. Kim, and J. M. Noh. "A study on evaluation of pebble flow velocity with modification of the kinematic model for pebble bed reactor." *Annals of Nuclear Energy* (2013).
- [6] L. Desideri. *Development and Validation of a Python-Based Probabilistic Tool for Simulating Pebble Motion in Pebble Bed Reactors*. Master's thesis, Sapienza University of Rome (2025).